

EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

EUYD11 Results of the Consultation Phase: Connecting the EU with Youth

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People Dialogue and Change

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Chapter 1: Introduction and Summary

The 11th cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue (EUYD11) runs from 1st of January 2025 to 30th of June 2026 under the Trio Presidency of Poland – Denmark – Cyprus. This document contains the results of the EUYD11 Consultation.

The thematic framework of the 11th cycle is the EU Youth Goal #1 - Connecting the EU with Youth. The ambition is to foster a sense of youth belonging to the European project and build a bridge between the EU and young people to regain trust and increase participation.

National Working Groups (NWGs) from all EU countries conducted the consultation using a common framework. NWGs engaged an estimated **38,042 young people**. Consultation participants were also highly diverse:

- 92.1% of participants reported that this was the first time they had engaged in EUYD, an increase from the previous cycle.
- A greater proportion of young people from lower socio-economic backgrounds took part compared to the previous cycle. 56.6% of participants in this cycle had no parent with a university degree.
- Similar to previous cycles, various minority groups are still over-represented (ethnic minority, sexual minority, religious minority and persons with disabilities).
- Similar to previous cycles, rural youth are still under-represented, although just under a quarter of participants were still from rural areas.
- Men and women are increasingly more equally represented compared to previous cycles, though some over-representation of women is still present. 54% of participants were young women.

A range of consultation methods were used; nearly all NWGs undertook face-to-face consultation activities. Alongside this, over two-thirds undertook a survey using common questions (the EUYD11 Standardised Survey), and some also undertook a range of other methods, such as social media polls and online meetings.

In addition to the NWG consultation, five International Non-Governmental Youth Organisations (INGYOs), as well as eleven National Youth Councils (NYCs) from EU candidacy or potential candidacy countries, supplied expert statements.

The consultation was built around six key questions:

1. How can we ensure that all young people in the EU feel a sense of belonging to Europe and of being a part of the EU?
2. How can we make sure all people in the EU share common EU values?
3. How can we build trust between young people and democracy within the EU?
4. Across the EU, how can we make sure new laws, policies and decisions are youth-friendly?
5. How can we better use the Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps programmes to support young people to become active citizens?

6. What updates might be needed to the European Youth Goals, as part of revising the EU Youth Strategy?

Variations on these questions were used to guide the IYNGO and NYC expert statements.

This report contains a summary of the various reports received from NWGs, IYNGOs, and NYCs, as well as results of the EUYD11 Standardised Survey, structured around the guiding questions above.

The headline results of the consultation are:

In the view of young people, the sense of belonging and trust in the EU, as well as support for EU values, can be built by:

- Increasing transparency of EU decision-making and demonstrating the relevance and impact of EU institutions on young people's day-to-day lives. Using communication campaigns from EU institutions to promote EU values and provide young people with better access to information on EU decision-making.
- Improving civic education, especially within schools, on topics related to Europe and the EU, such as values and functioning of EU institutions.
- Strengthening young people's democratic voice and influence on policy-making, by enhancing youth participation and representation of young people's voices in EU decision-making.

The last of these measures is also central to youth-friendly policy-making, where there is a need to ensure that new policies in all fields demonstrate long-term, future-oriented thinking and consider the needs, voices, and impact upon young people. This is said to require strengthening mechanisms for youth participation in policy-making, informal dialogue between young people and decision makers, youth impact assessments and youth checks, increasing the number of young decision makers and politicians, as well as an attitudinal shift amongst policy makers.

Throughout all of these areas, to bring the EU closer to youth there is a need to more consistently uphold the EU values across and beyond the Union, as well as to deliver policy and policymaking that better improves the social and economic well-being of young people.

The Erasmus+ and ESC programmes, though evidently valued by young people who took part, can be improved by more explicit terms of strengthening the civic education dimension as well as enhancing the accessibility and inclusion of young people from all backgrounds.

There is potential interest in revising and updating some of the EU Youth Goals, though the Goals are still widely supported. New topics may need to be addresses, such as peace and security, digitalisation, and economic wellbeing.

Chapter 2: Ensuring a Sense of Belonging to Europe and the EU

The first part of the consultation was based around the following guiding question: ‘How can we ensure that all young people in the EU feel a sense of belonging to Europe and of being a part of the EU?’¹ This section explores the results linked to this question.

European Identity and Attachment to Europe

In the EUYD11 Standardised Survey, **about 60% of young people feel totally or to a large extent attached to Europe and a European identity** (Figure 2.2). This result is the same for young people with fewer opportunities (i.e., those who belong to various minorities).

(Figure 2.2)

(Figure 2.3)

However, there is a substantial difference in the case of young people coming from high and low economic backgrounds. **While 41% of those who are financially comfortable feel totally attached to Europe, only 19% of young people from less financially comfortable backgrounds feel totally European.** The graph also well illustrates that this difference is not

¹non-EU NYCs were asked ‘What actions need to be taken to ensure that all young people in countries joining the EU feel a sense of belonging to Europe and of being a part of the EU?’

only present between the most well-off and those least comfortable, but that there is a visible trend of increasing bonds to Europe with increasing economic stability (Figure 2.3)

Within the qualitative consultation, young people described **a sense of national identity both competing and co-existing with their European identity**. The extent to which young people felt European was described as varying between different young people and linked to awareness, direct experience with EU initiatives, and access to inclusive, accessible opportunities. For some, being European is an assumed matter; for others, their primary identity is connected to their home country. NWGs often described how young people in more marginalised circumstances felt a more substantial disconnect from Europe and the EU.

Connection to the EU and European Institutions

The concepts of Europe, the European Union, and the EU Institutions were often used as interchangeable terms within the consultation dialogues. For many young people within the EU, a sense of connection to 'Europe' was understood as a sense of connection to the EU institutions and their policymaking.

In this context, several NWG reports described how **young people often perceive the EU as 'far away' and do not feel a strong connection to it**. For many, the EU is not only perceived as politically distant but also culturally unrelatable. Young people often do not see their own values, backgrounds, or realities reflected in the EU leadership, communication, or priorities. This lack of recognition deepens the sense of disconnection. Some described how the EU is associated with political language and abstract ideals that do not align with their everyday concerns,

'Young people mentioned a sense of emotional and cultural detachment from the European Union. For many, the EU remains a distant and abstract structure, perceived more as a political or economic institution than as a tangible presence in their everyday lives.'

Spanish NWG Report

'For many young people, Europe comes across as a complicated and far-off system, often leaving them feeling overwhelmed. "I just found an Insta account about Europe that explains everything. I'd never even looked it up before." This sense of confusion is made worse by the feeling that there's a big gap between ordinary young people and the institutions, which are sometimes seen as "a huge bureaucracy, miles away from real life." For some, being part of the European Union feels abstract, hard to put into words. "That's just too complicated a question; we're not taught enough about it at school to be able to answer.'

French NWG Report

Several NWG reports described the barriers that create this sense of disconnection. According to NWGs, participants identified a **lack of understanding and information on the operations** of the EU, its decision-making and EU politics. The EU is sometimes perceived as complex, closed off, **lacking in transparency** and **distant from day-to-day realities**.

Linked to this are concerns that the **EU policymaking fails to adequately consider the views or concerns of young people**, contributing to feelings of disempowerment and

disengagement. There was a broad discussion of the lack of representation of young people within the EU policymaking, both in terms of inadequate mechanisms for youth participation and a lack of serious consideration of the day-to-day lives of young people.

A smaller number of NWGs also highlighted concerns about how the **benefits of the EU membership are not felt equally by all citizens**, particularly those from marginalised groups who do not have their rights respected. The influence of **anti-EU media narratives** was also raised. There were concerns that young people are sometimes exposed to one-sided or negative portrayals of the EU in local media or through politically motivated narratives.

Considering the future of Europe, young people in the consultation expressed a desire for an EU where **Europe becomes a lived reality, visible in classrooms, communities and conversations**. They wish to see the principles of the EU put into practice more strongly to shape a fairer and more peaceful future. They emphasise the importance of equality, respect, and greater political participation for young people, and call for more transparency, information accessibility, and accountability of decision-makers. For many, it seems that building European democracy at the grassroots and **an EU which responds more effectively to the concerns of young people** is central to their sense of belonging and support for the European project.

Measures to Build a Sense of Belonging

A range of measures to build a sense of belonging to the EU and Europe was suggested across the consultation.

1) Increasing transparency of EU decision-making and improving young people's access to information on EU decision-making

A need to make a larger effort in communicating what the EU does for young people, the opportunities provided, and how political decisions are made was stressed. There was a desire for **more accessible, straightforward, and relevant information** about the EU programs, opportunities created for young people, how European institutions work and what impact they have on young people's lives.

Communication campaigns should show the relevance and **impact of the EU institutions on young people's day-to-day lives**. It was said to be important to 'speak the language' of young people and engage through platforms, language, and formats that reflect their realities, needs and interests, grounding the communication in the day-to-day concerns of young people, as well as to show how young people influence decision making.

'Make the EU more present in everyday life.'

Swedish NWG Report

The need for **transparent and balanced information** about the benefits of the EU membership was stressed, as well as the importance of **youth-friendly, accessible communication** (short videos, podcasts, social media content, or influencer collaborations) tailored to different age groups and educational backgrounds.

‘According to them, youth need to actively know what the EU does - what is provided to them personally and directly by the EU.’

Slovakian NWG Report

Considering the **methods and modes of communication**, the use of social media, information sessions on school curricula, outreach through youth organisations and the establishment of EU info points and ambassadors were all suggested.

2) Improving civic education related to Europe and the EU

There were widespread calls for improvements to civic education and teaching about Europe. It was felt there was a need to provide more extensive education relating to:

- **Functioning of the EU institutions** - their role, work of MEPS and **their impact** on day-to-day lives,
- **How young people can influence the EU institutions and policymaking,**
- **Young people's rights and civic responsibilities,**
- **European identity and values** (see section: Values)
- **European history, culture and language**

The main emphasis was on **improving civic education within schools**, either as a standalone subject and as modules within school curricula or integrated into other subjects. However, proposals for interactive visits to the EU institutions, workshops, and local community building projects were also made. There were also calls for better use of Europe Day, European Museum Night, and a European Youth Festival.

3) Creating opportunities for international cultural exchanges

The value of international mobility schemes such as Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps was highlighted as a tool for building a sense of European belonging. Connecting with peers from other EU countries was said to help break down stereotypes and foster mutual understanding (See section: EU Youth Programmes).

‘Travel and exchange opportunities were seen as essential for experiencing and strengthening a sense of shared European identity.’

Danish NWG Report

4) Enhancing youth participation and representation of young people’s voices in the EU decision-making

Consultation replies highlighted the need for more opportunities for young people to participate in shaping the EU of today and tomorrow, to promote a sense of ownership and connection. It was said that sense of belonging is tied to feeling heard and represented in EU decision-making, and clearer pathways for youth participation would help build trust and engagement. Specific suggestions included votes at 16, strengthening of youth councils, more consultation opportunities, and more opportunities for direct dialogue with decision makers. Emphasis was placed on transparency, the ability of the participatory mechanism to influence policy and the importance of feedback. In this sense, the results mirrored the findings of the [EUYD8 Consultation](#) regarding the desired types of mechanisms.

Alongside the more specific measures above, some NWGS highlighted how the EU cultivated a sense of belonging when **taking actions on issues that were of strong concern to young people**. For example, the Irish NWG highlighted the importance of tackling discrimination and inequality and the impact on the sense of belonging for young people experiencing these issues.

'A clear message was that young people feel prouder of Europe when the EU shows that it is tackling big challenges that matter to them: climate change, affordable housing, rising living costs, inclusion, and equality.'

Maltese NWG Report

Chapter 3: Sharing the EU Values

The second part of the consultation explored the following question: *'How can we make sure all people in the EU share common EU values?'* The EU values are laid out in Article 2 of the Lisbon Treaty and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. The Union is founded on the values of:

- Respect for human dignity,
- Freedom,
- Democracy,
- Equality,
- The rule of law, and
- Respect for human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities

This section summarises the replies given to this question across the various reports.

Young People's Understanding of the EU Values

Within the qualitative consultation, **some reports identified that young people were uncertain of what is meant by the EU values.** It was described that participants were unfamiliar with the term 'EU values' but were often able to mention values as democracy, freedom, equality, and the rule of law as examples when promoted. However, young participants also mentioned other related terms such as transparency, peace, freedom of movement, and solidarity, which are not, strictly speaking, the EU values as specified by Article 2 of the Lisbon Treaty and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. There was a sense that, **whilst young people understand the individual values** and related concepts, **the idea that the EU has a specific set of defined values is less widely understood** and known.

'One of the key conclusions is that not all participants were familiar with the common values of the EU. This ties in with one of the main proposals – if these values are to be shared and upheld, citizens should be familiar with them.'

Slovakian NWG Report

Support for the EU Values

All of the EU values are totally or largely important to young people who took part in the EUYD11 standardised survey, with the rates of approval between 80% and 93% (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1

There is a range of patterns between different groups of young people:

- **Freedom** is slightly more important for women (79% totally agree) than for men (73% totally agree), and it is much more important for financially comfortable young people (78% totally agree) than for those less financially comfortable (58% agree).
- **Respect for human rights** is slightly more important for young people with fewer opportunities (79% totally agree) than for the majority youth (76% totally agree). It is also more important for women (79% totally agree) than for men (65% totally agree), and it is much more important for financially comfortable young people (71% totally agree) than for those less financially comfortable (56% agree).
- **Respect for human dignity** is more important for women (78% totally agree) than for men (62% totally agree), and it is more important for financially comfortable young people (68% totally agree) than for those less fortunate (51% agree).
- **Democracy** is slightly more important for women (69% totally agree) than for men (63% totally agree), and it is more important for financially comfortable young people (64% totally agree) than for those less financially comfortable (46% agree).
- **Equality** is more important for young people with fewer opportunities (71% totally agree) than to majority youth (66% totally agree), it is much more important for women (73% totally agree) than men (54% totally agree), and it is more important for financially

comfortable young people (65% totally agree) than for those less financially comfortable (44% agree).

- **The rule of law** is much more important for financially comfortable young people (64% totally agree) than for those less financially comfortable young people (44% agree).
- **The rights of persons belonging to minorities** are more important for young people with fewer opportunities (63% totally agree) than for majority youth (52% totally agree), and it is much more important for women (64% totally agree) than for men (44% totally agree).

The qualitative consultation also revealed complex relationships between young people and the EU values. There were concerns that **values were not equally shared in all countries, and by all people** (especially on the right wing), and values were not always upheld in practice.

'Many young people consider the values of the EU—such as democracy, freedom, equality, and human rights—to be important and worth supporting. They associate the EU with security, shared freedoms, and supranational cohesion. At the same time, they criticise the lack of consistent implementation of these values in political practice. In their view, the rise of right-wing parties, growing societal divisions, and a lack of political participation undermine the credibility and lived reality of EU principles.'

Austrian NWG Report

The theme that the values were not upheld in practice was commonly raised, especially about **the rights and experiences of minority groups**:

'Young people in Sweden from different backgrounds experience injustice, for example, in education and the labour market. This creates a sense that the EU's fundamental principles of equality and non-discrimination do not apply to everyone.'

Swedish NWG Report

'[Young people] highlight rising racial and religious intolerance and the impact of stereotypes on society's perceptions (e.g., the belief that all Roma are violent and resistant to assimilation). Views on migrants are divided—some feel they are discriminated against, while others believe they have too many rights. A similar perception exists towards the Roma community.'

Slovenian NWG Report

'Young people from migrant backgrounds or ethnic minorities argued that EU values like equality and human dignity often feel like promises that are not fully delivered.'

Maltese NWG Report

'Young people with fewer opportunities, including those in vocational education, with a migration background, living in rural areas, or facing socio-economic hardship, expressed concerns about the way EU values are promoted and practised. Many of them said that values like equality, solidarity, and dignity often feel aspirational rather than real in their lives. A recurring issue was the disconnect between EU values and daily experiences of exclusion or discrimination.'

Dutch NWG Report

Democratic Debate and Polarisation

Within the qualitative consultation, some concerns were expressed about **rising polarisation and loss of tolerance and mutual respect**. This was said to be partly linked to misinformation and social media, but also to a disconnect between local or national values and the EU values. There was concern about the politicisation of the EU values and their use within national political debates. Some NWGs highlighted young people's concerns about a shift towards cultural identity politics and *'fighting because of differences'*. This was said to be fuelled by rising social inequality and economic pressure, as well as the ongoing global crisis. These things were believed to make it more challenging to engage openly in discussion and debates about values. According to the Polish NWG, young people are concerned that *'EU Values are associated with particular parties or ideologies rather than with a shared European identity. This creates a divisive environment in which young people feel pressured to "choose sides" instead of understanding values as common ground.'*

Within this, **some young people in the consultation were keen not to have particular viewpoints imposed upon them**. The Estonian NWG described a minority of young people with *'conservative or hesitant attitudes'* who expressed challenges in accepting rapidly changing gender norms. The Romanian NWG highlighted how young people from rural areas in their consultation stated support for the EU values, but also held intolerant or exclusionary views towards specific groups, such as LGBTQ young people. The Polish NWG described young people's feeling that the EU values are sometimes imposed upon national culture and identity, and how *'many [young people] feel caught between broader European narratives and the dominant attitudes in their local communities, including in families and schools.'* Rightly or wrongly, it seems that for some young people supporting the EU values is associated with adopting particular viewpoints (often about persons belonging to minorities) which they themselves do not necessarily perceive as universal values.

Figure 3.2

While the **concerns about loss of democratic culture may be common amongst young people, the results of the EUYD11 standardised survey show that the majority of young people regularly meet peers with differing opinions, and they feel able to have debates with them** (Figure 3.2). Over half of young people who took the survey stated they regularly meet people with opposite worldviews. Over 70% of them feel able to have a debate with people holding opposite worldviews. Young men say they are more likely to meet people voicing opposite worldviews (21% totally agree) than women (15% totally agree), and men also feel much more able to have discussions with such people (39% totally agree) than women (27% totally agree).

Promoting the EU Values

To increase support for the EU values, a range of measures was suggested across the following general areas:

Fostering safe spaces for debate and dialogue - the need to create safe spaces, both online and offline, for young people to engage in constructive discussion with people with opposing views or from other cultures, was highlighted. It was seen that reintroducing a culture of debate was key to building mutual respect and tolerance. This culture was desired not just for young people, but for parts of society, especially amongst politicians and political actors. Consultation reports were often nonspecific about the mechanisms or programs that could be used to create this. International exchanges such as the Erasmus+ were cited as a tool for promoting intercultural dialogue. Still, the importance of digital spaces and non-commercial spaces was also discussed, as well as educational spaces.

Improving civic education was the most widely proposed solution for promotion of the EU values. Multiple reports highlighted participants who said they had learnt nothing in school about the EU values, or when they did, it was presented in a dry theoretical way. The need to embed teaching about the EU values and civic education more broadly into school curricula, using interactive, engaging, and non-formal learning methods, was widely stated. It was said to be important that such education created safe spaces for debate, was non-partisan and covered such issues as how the EU institutions work, and critical thinking, alongside learning about the EU values themselves.

'These values must be taught in school. The role of citizenship education classes is crucial in building a common value system.'

Bulgarian NWG Report

Communication campaigns from EU institutions to promote the EU values were also highlighted as a solution. This sits alongside the calls for better communication and transparency regarding the EU decision-making (see sections on Belonging and Trust), with a strong emphasis on effective use of social media and accessible language. However, in the context of the EU values, the importance of communications campaigns to combat misinformation and disinformation was also highlighted. The Maltese NWG noted suggestions from young people for *'youth ambassadors, influencers, or content creators who could share positive messages about EU values in ways that appeal to young audiences.'*

‘There was also a clear call for more practical and relatable communication about EU values, using formats and channels accessible to youth. Participants suggested that the EU should engage young people through storytelling, real-life examples, and grassroots initiatives that make values tangible and relevant, rather than abstract concepts distant from daily realities.’

Spanish NWG Report

Stronger approaches to tackling disinformation were also called for. Young people expressed frustration that manipulative content often distorts the meaning of the EU values, presenting them as foreign, harmful, or threatening to national traditions. The Kosovar youth council proposed *‘counter disinformation and nationalist narratives through youth-led fact-checking initiatives and digital literacy campaigns.’* Other consultation reports emphasised the need for better media information literacy education for young people, and the general feeling that the EU should intervene more significantly to combat hate speech in information, such as through stronger regulation of social media.

‘[Young people] seek stronger protection against harmful propaganda (e.g., dehumanisation and human rights violations in wars), recognising that such propaganda undermines core EU values.’

Slovenian NWG Report

The need for the EU values to be consistently upheld by all member states, and the EU, in both international and domestic contexts, was identified as an important step in building support for the EU values. It was said that young people need to see the values consistently applied by the EU and that when people feel excluded, economically insecure, or neglected by institutions, values like solidarity or democracy may appear distant or abstract. Some also stated they need to see political leaders and institutions set an example by demonstrating these values in their daily work. In line with this, there were calls for greater action to reduce discrimination and inequality, provide greater protection for minority groups and women and to reduce unequal access to opportunities such as work and housing. It was said that the EU values need to be upheld in everyday life, not just in theory.

‘While values such as democracy and freedom are generally widely supported, young people perceive significant shortcomings regarding minority rights and anti-discrimination—often due to personal experiences of racism or social exclusion. They also demand greater social and economic justice. Furthermore, they call for more political credibility and consistency.’

Austrian NWG Report

A key part of upholding EU values for many young people was also the **strengthening of young people’s democratic voice and participatory mechanisms**. According to the Danish NWG *‘Many felt that when their voices are genuinely heard and their concerns reflected in policies, they develop a stronger sense of ownership over EU values.’* It was also highlighted that participatory activities, such as those run by youth organisations, are both a source of values and a way to have access to them. (For further details on strengthening participation mechanisms, see the sections on Trust and Belonging).

Chapter 4: Building Trust Between Young People and Democracy Within the EU

The third part of the consultation was based around the following guiding question: *'How can we build trust between young people and democracy within the EU?'* This section explores the results linked to this question.

Levels of Trust

Overall, 45% of the young people who took part in the EUYD11 standardised survey trust the EU institutions either totally or to a large extent (Figure 4.1). This differs in young people coming from financially comfortable backgrounds, who trust the EU institutions more (15% totally agree and 34% agree to a large extent), compared with young people from less comfortable financial backgrounds (8% totally agree and 28% agree to a large extent). In the qualitative consultation, several reports highlighted how young people felt that building trust was connected to effective policies and improving the social and economic well-being of young people. By addressing concerns such as affordable housing, access to stable and meaningful employment, providing security, fairness and dignity, European democracy was able to flourish and be trusted by young people.

Figure 4.1

Barriers to Trust

Within the qualitative consultation, a range of barriers to trust were identified across two broad areas of concern:

- **A perception that the EU is not sufficiently focused on young people or issues of concern to young people.** The political focus is seen as prioritising older generations over youth and lacking in long-term or youth-oriented thinking. There are concerns that there is a lack of inclusion of young people in decision-making, with too few young people being visibly represented in institutions. This is linked to a perception that economic and political interests outweigh democratic values. Young people feel that their voices are not taken seriously, that they lack real influence, and that power struggles dominate politics. They often feel their voices are not genuinely heard or valued, that the EU does not take action, or is too slow to respond to critical issues of concern for young people and the future.

'The EU often talks about issues like climate change and racism, but doesn't act sufficiently. They perceive that politicians are more focused on elections (getting re-elected) and personal gain, leading to slow responses on critical issues.'

Irish NWG Report

- **Lack of transparency and accountability within the EU decision-making.** Consultation respondents described a lack of accountability on the part of decision-makers, which was said to cause a loss of trust or even distrust among young people. Concern was expressed about corruption and fraud scandals. Linked to this was the idea that **the EU was hard to understand**, mainly due to a lack of accessible and engaging information. Some young people perceive political processes as distant, non-transparent and indifferent to their input.

'While many young people value the EU in principle, they often feel disconnected from its procedures and doubtful of their own influence within them.'

Czech NWG Report

A smaller number of consultation reports identified how **anti-EU political discourse** at the national level also plays a role in damaging perceptions of the EU, as well as **fake news** and misinformation from online media sources. Concerns that the EU was **not taking strong enough stances on human rights issues** (such as discrimination within the EU, or of conflicts within Ukraine and Palestine) were also expressed - it was said that this was a source of *'double standards'* and this failure to uphold the EU values was damaging to trust.

Methods of Increasing Trust

In the EUYD11 standardised survey, young people were asked a question about which measures would help build trust in the EU institutions. Results show all of the listed measures were important for young people who filled in the survey (Figure 4.2). The most important measures are accountability of policymakers (81% totally or to a large extent agree), and

availability of information on policymaking processes, contemporary topics, and political priorities (over 75% totally or to a large extent agree).

Women were often more positive in their answers than men, stressing the importance of almost all of these measures. A similar situation can also be seen in the case of young people from financially comfortable backgrounds compared with young people from less comfortable financial backgrounds.

Figure 4.2

At an abstract level, many of the consultation reports described how trust could be built by the EU, **demonstrating more clearly how decisions are made** (transparency) and by **increased accountability amongst politicians and policy makers**. According to the Finnish NWG, *‘trust would be strengthened especially if politicians were to take more responsibility for their decisions.’* The Greek NWG commented that according to young people, *‘institutions must therefore uphold accountability, integrity and the rule of law, visibly applying EU values to policies that affect young people’s lives’*. For many, this issue is related to how the EU institutions communicate.

'[Young people] said that they are more likely to trust institutions that are clear about their positions—even when they disagree—than those that use vague language or avoid accountability. Political ambiguity or populist messaging aimed at pleasing everyone was viewed as a sign of weakness, not strength. In contrast, direct and authentic communication, especially when delivered in a youth-friendly and accessible format, helps create a sense of mutual respect.'

Polish NWG Report

'The participants admitted that they do not feel like they have a sufficient understanding of how the processes inside of the EU institutions work, how it makes decisions and adopts policies. They mentioned that even though they might try or are interested in learning how the EU operates, the processes are too confusing and not transparent enough.'

Slovakian NWG Report

On a practical basis, there was said to be a strong need for **more effective communication about decision-making from EU institutions**. The need for clear, accessible, engaging and non-partisan information was repeatedly emphasised. Consultation participants stressed the importance of relatable language and reporting that was easy to find and understand. *'Young people want updates not in bureaucratic language or official reports'* (Cyprus NWG Report). The role of social media, especially TikTok and Instagram, was heavily stressed, and there was a clear desire for the EU institutions to use these channels of communication more effectively and more extensively. It was said to be important that communication campaigns explained decisions publicly and made decision-making processes clearer, as well as showing how the EU impacts day-to-day lives. The need to show how young people can influence decisions and the impact of this was also highlighted.

Demonstrating the relevance of the EU to the day-to-day lives of young people was frequently discussed across the consultation. *'Many young people feel the EU is a confusing system with low output but high costs. They need to learn about the real impact and what the EU actually does for them.'* (German NWG Report) It was said there is a need to highlight the real-life benefits of the EU membership and policies for young people, such as mobility, study, and work opportunities.

For many consulted young people, developing trust in the EU was also about **increasing the influence that young people have over the EU-level decision-making**, as well as the opportunities to participate in it. They called for inclusive participation formats that reach broader groups and have more meaningful influence on political decision-making. Concrete suggestions for this included:

- boosting digital formats for youth participation,
- introducing youth representatives within the EU institutions, youth quotas in political bodies and enhanced leadership positions for young people in political parties,
- strengthening the role of the National and Local Youth Councils, as well as of the European Youth Forum,
- introducing dedicated mechanisms for involving young people in the EU institutions and decisions, such as youth advisory boards, participatory budgeting, deliberative assemblies or citizen panels,
- lowering the voting age to 16,

- boosting exchanges between decision-makers and young people, and
- creating ongoing consultation exercises (rather than on-off).

The emphasis was on **expanding the current opportunities for participation and increasing the visibility and accessibility** of these to more young people. Above all, there was said to be a need to **increase the influence** that young people have and to provide **meaningful feedback** on their impact on decision-making. Existing participatory channels are seen as “*very distant*.” Many young people expected follow-ups on results of participatory processes and more transparency on the implementation of these results, as well as making the participatory structures accessible and representative of all youth, not just the most confident or politically active. This was said to be of particular concern for young people with fewer opportunities or marginalised young people who sometimes felt more disconnected from existing structures of youth representation.

‘Young people across the EU believe that trust in democracy is built when they feel engaged and informed. They want to understand political processes, see the relevance of their opinions, and have the opportunity to meet politicians. According to young people, trust in democracy within the European Union can be cultivated by providing understanding, hands-on experience, and meaningful participation.’

Latvian NWG Report

Some consultation reports also stressed the need for political decision makers and older generations to **take the rights and views of young people more seriously**, suggesting that intergenerational dialogue, as well as a general shift in attitudes to young people, might support this.

‘Rebuilding trust necessitates a rights-based, redistributive and participatory governance framework that recognises young people not as beneficiaries, but as full-fledged political actors.’

Turkish NYC Report

In line with results from previous consultation questions, there were calls to **strengthen civic education** across Europe as a way of building trust. Education was framed as a tool to increase understanding of how the EU works, and to make Europe and European institutions more visible. Education was said to be able to foster a practical understanding of democratic procedures and help youth see their role in shaping Europe, especially with a focus on practical skills, critical thinking, and opportunities to practice democratic engagement in real life. Emphasis was placed on improving the standard of political and civic education in schools, embedding topics within curricula and starting from an early age.

‘Young participants called for comprehensive civic and political education, starting from an early age, integrated into formal curricula and delivered through engaging, participatory methods. Schools should go beyond theory to provide practical skills such as debating, organising and scrutinising policy. Civic responsibility, critical thinking and media literacy must also be cultivated to help youth understand their rights, how institutions operate and how they can actively shape public life.’

Greek NWG Report

Chapter 5: Youth Friendly Policies

The fourth part of the consultation was based around the following guiding question: ‘*Across the EU, how can we make sure new laws, policies and decisions are youth-friendly?*’ This section explores the results linked to this question. For simplicity, within this section, the term policy is used in the broadest sense to refer to laws, policies, strategies, regulations and any other related mechanisms.

How Do Young People See It?

Only 34% of the young people who took part in the EUYD11 standardised survey totally or to a large extent agree that the needs and concerns of youth are taken into account in the EU policymaking. About half of them think their needs are taken into account only to a small extent, and a further 17% believe they are not taken into account at all (Figure 5.1)

Moreover, young people from less comfortable financial backgrounds are even more sceptical (29% totally or to a large extent agree) than those who are financially comfortable (38% totally or to a large extent agree).

Figure 5.1

What Is a Youth-friendly Policy?

The consultation question guidance encouraged respondents to explore what young people understand under the term youth-friendly policy. Across the several reports, a number of comments contribute to defining this concept. It was said that a youth friendly policy is:

- **Future-oriented**, contributing to long-term goals, for the benefit of the future of young people, and assessed for its impact on future generations.
- **Created with, not for, young people**, taking the voices and concerns of young people seriously through meaningful consultation and engagement. A key feature of this was recognising the specific voices and involvement of young people in more marginalised circumstances.

- **Well communicated** in clear, accessible language to ensure that the policy is understandable to a wide range of people.
- Policy which **improves the lives of young people and addresses their core concerns**. ‘A law or decision is perceived as “youth friendly” only if it produces visible improvements in their daily lives’ (Spanish NWG Report)

What Measures Can Encourage Youth-Friendly Policy?

Young people who took part in the EUYD11 standardised survey consider all of the measures suggested in the survey to be highly relevant, with the shares of those who totally or to a large extent agree only slightly varying between 75% and 78% (Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.2

However, there seemed to be some **differences relating to young people in more marginalised circumstances**. Young people from less financially comfortable backgrounds, young people with fewer opportunities, and young people who are not in education,

employment, or training (NEET) were *more supportive* of regular consultations with young people than their counterparts. Furthermore, young people in less financially comfortable positions seemed to place less emphasis on international dialogue, contact between policy makers and young people, having more young policymakers, and regular consultation with youth organisations. Comparing genders, **young women** were slightly more supportive of consulting youth organisations, youth advisory bodies, and regular contact with politicians than young men.

Within the qualitative consultations, a range of proposals for how we can ensure future politics are youth-friendly were made and described in detail. These can be grouped into the following themes:

1. Increasing and strengthening mechanisms for youth participation in policy-making

‘For laws and policies to be truly youth-friendly, young people must be involved meaningfully and continuously throughout the policymaking process, not only as passive recipients of policy but as co-creators and active stakeholders.’

Dutch NWG Report

This theme was widely raised. It was said there is a need to **include a diverse range of young people** through a wide **range of participatory formats** (e.g., digital platforms and apps, consultation in schools, youth centres and public spaces, advisory boards, youth parliament, youth councils, elected youth organisations, structured dialogue). Some reports also stressed the need for a mandatory basis for participatory mechanisms and increased funding for them. The need for **continuous rather than one-off involvement** in policy-making was highlighted. Participatory mechanisms should *involve young people in all stages of policy making, from ‘design and consultation to implementation and evaluation’*. Linked to this was the **lack of meaningful influence on decisions**, as well as **lack of transparent feedback loops** showing how youth input influences decisions.

2. Informal dialogue between young people and decision makers

Alongside the role of structured participation mechanisms, the additional importance of informal dialogue with politicians and young people was widely discussed.

‘Young people stress the need for regular and structured dialogue with decision-makers. Popular and effective formats for such exchanges include initiatives like “Coffee with Politicians,” where young people can voice their opinions in an informal setting.’

Latvian NWG Report

3. Youth impact assessments and youth checks

These were commonly suggested and described as a tool to evaluate how proposed legislation would affect young people’s rights, well-being and future prospects.

4. [Increasing the number of young decision makers and politicians](#)

This was said to be achievable through the use of **youth quotas** in decision-making bodies, but also through providing additional support and **encouragement** for young people to enter politics and advance through political parties. The potential of lowering the voting age to 16 was also noted. Many young people with fewer opportunities also highlighted that the need for stronger representation was not just about age, but also about diversity (e.g. young people from ethnic minority backgrounds wishing to see politicians from more ethnic minority backgrounds).

5. [Increasing the general systems of support for young people to participate](#)

Alongside the measures above, it was highlighted that **such mechanisms need young people to be informed and engaged in policy-making**. Thus, there were further calls to **enhance the systems of support** that encourage young people's participation in general. These included the need to **improve civic education** and **information about the EU decision-making** (as discussed in the previous chapter). They also noted the value of investing in spaces for youth participation, such as youth organisations, debating opportunities and active civil learning opportunities.

6. [Mainstreaming the concerns of young people into all areas of policymaking](#)

Several reports highlighted that youth-friendly policymaking should not just be confined to youth policy. There was a need to **consider young people in all areas of policymaking**.

'It is important to note that such involvement should extend beyond traditional "youth policies" and include all political themes across, whether youth-specific policies or broader areas like trade, defence, and the economy, since all affect young people's lives and futures. Their input in these broader policy areas should be valued equally, ensuring their perspectives shape decisions that impact their present and future.'

Danish NWG Report.

7. [A shift in attitude amongst policy makers and politicians](#)

Finally, many reports noted that creating more youth-friendly policies required a change in attitude from politicians and decision makers, and the **genuine political will** to take into account the voices and needs of young people in policymaking.

'The quality and ambition of youth-friendly decisions depend on the political will of decision-makers and their legal institutionalisation.'

German NWG Report

Chapter 6: Active Citizenship and the EU Youth Programmes

The fifth part of the consultation was based around the following guiding question: *‘How can we better use the Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps programmes to support young people to become active citizens?’* This section explores the results linked to this question. The analysis is organised by themes specified for the Danish EU Youth Conference².

Across the consultation, it was clear that Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps are both highly valued programmes, and many consultation reports highlighted young people's positive experience of these programmes as well as the impact they have. The purpose of the consultation is not to evaluate these programmes, but rather to identify potential improvements for future programmes. As such, the reporting below focuses on identifying the current challenges and possible improvements, and it should not be treated as evaluative.

The EU Youth Programmes and Youth Organisations

The topic of youth organisations was not widely commented upon within replies to the consultation question on the EU youth programmes, but it was clear that youth organisations were understood to be one of many key stakeholders in the programme. Some respondents emphasised the need for **continuity of support and funding** for youth organisations to enhance the EU youth programmes overall.

“We can better use Erasmus+ by increasing the amount of money available to youth organisations, increas[ing] the number of staff to support organisations in national agencies making applications and ensure a wider and more diverse group of young people get to participate.”

Young person responding to the Irish NWG

Others called for dedicated funding for specific types of youth organisations, such as those supporting LGBTQ youth.

The challenges that **smaller grassroots youth organisations** have in accessing EU youth programme grants were emphasised by other respondents. This was said to be caused by the administrative complexity of the programmes (see topic: Administrative and technical barriers). At the same time, some NWGs emphasised how young people who were involved with youth organisations were more able to access the EU youth programmes and were concerned with the programmes reaching beyond these groups.

NYCs outside of the EU and IYNGOs emphasised the critical role that the EU youth programmes played in terms of **protecting the shrinking space for youth civil society** and supporting rights-based organisations. Linked to this concern, there were calls for the prioritisation of rights-based and youth organisations, especially those working with marginalised groups or in politically sensitive areas. The role that the programmes could play

² The section on sports is not included, there were no substantive responses on this topic.

in supporting these organisations was stressed by several NYCs and IYNGOs (see topic: Addressing New Challenges).

A small number of consultation replies also called for the **strengthening of training and mobility opportunities for youth workers** provided through the EU youth programmes.

The EU Youth Programmes and Formal Education

Considering the role of formal education with the EU youth programmes, three main themes emerged across the consultation replies:

- 1) Better utilising schools and formal education as a tool for outreach and promotion.** Schools and other parts of formal education were often described as mechanisms through which outreach and sharing of information about the EU youth programme opportunities could be enhanced (see topic: Awareness). It was said that there was a need to change the perception that Erasmus+ was primarily a university exchange for academically competent students. Concerns were also raised about schools limiting participation opportunities to academically able students.
- 2) Embedding the EU youth programmes as part of citizenship education in schools and formal education.** Linked to the above, it was identified that the EU youth programmes should be embedded into civic education within schools and formal education. This was part of wider calls within other parts of the consultation to address the topic of the EU directly within civic education and to demonstrate better the opportunities the EU provides to young people.
- 3) Improving recognition of participants' civic learning.** A range of consultation replies called for better recognition of non-formal learning outcomes and civic learning contributions made through Erasmus+ and ESC. This was said to allow for better integration of civic learning into formal education and the labour market. Several measures were proposed for this, such as improving the Youthpass or other micro-credential systems and integrating civic engagement activities and volunteering into the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS). Tools like the Youthpass and micro-credential systems should be expanded and better integrated into formal education and the labour market to validate non-formal learning outcomes.

A small number of consultation replies also highlighted the need for **better aligning Erasmus+ with the labour market** through more vocational and practice-based opportunities, such as internships, apprenticeships, and job-shadowing. It was said that young people in vocational paths often feel left out of international programmes, even though they are eager to gain skills and experience beyond their immediate environment.

The EU Youth Programmes, Youth Volunteering and Solidarity

A common call within the qualitative consultation was to **strengthen the opportunities provided for local volunteering and solidarity**, and to increase the local community impact of projects funded through the programmes. The Romanian NWG highlighted the need to *‘Support youth-led projects at the local level, so that young people can see the impact of the EU in their own communities’*.

The value of supporting young people to **engage at the local level**, through civic mini projects or youth-led campaigns or similar, **especially as a follow-on from an international mobility experience**, was widely highlighted. This was said to reinforce the idea that civic responsibility is ongoing and rooted both locally and transnationally.

Many participants felt motivated by their Erasmus+ or ESC experience but lacked direction after their project ended. It was said that local follow-on measures would help increase long-term civic engagement and maximise the impacts of the EU youth programmes. The desire was to enable young people to contribute meaningfully to their home communities either before departure or after returning.

‘Some [young people] suggested creating alumni networks or local action hubs, where young people could continue their engagement with the themes they explored during their Erasmus+ or ESC projects, such as climate action or inclusion. This would ensure the impact of the programme continues long after the mobility period ends.’

Maltese NWG Report

Various concrete suggestions for follow-on support were made, such as microgrants for participants presenting the outcomes of their work in schools and community spaces, and alumni networks and peer mentorships linked to volunteering themes. Emphasis was typically placed on enabling young people to contribute to addressing issues of concern in their local community, such as environmental clean-ups, supporting vulnerable people, combating discrimination, or initiatives on mental health.

Support for community-focused and community-based projects is visible also in the EUYD11 standardised survey (Figure 6.1), where 68% of young people agreed totally or to a large extent that such opportunities would help them make a difference in the society. Moreover, volunteering abroad is seen as an important way to make a difference by 60% of young people who took part in the EUYD11 standardised survey.

Figure 6.1

Horizontal Priorities of the EU Youth Programmes

Within the qualitative consultation, NWG and NYC reports did not comment specifically on which horizontal priorities are desired for the next generation of the EU youth programmes. However, across the various areas of discussion, it is clear that emphasis is placed on two themes.

- **Civic engagement and political participation** - with emphasis on promoting youth democratic participation, increasing civic engagement, and increasing understanding of the EU among young people.
- **Inclusion and diversity** - with emphasis on using the programmes to both provide support for young people with fewer opportunities, as well as on reducing polarisation, challenging racism and discrimination.

Some mention was made of sustainability and digitisation, but these were not prominent themes within the consultation replies. This may be a reflection of the consultation question, which asked about active citizenship and did not specifically address these areas.

The EU Youth Programmes and Citizenship Skills

60% to 71% of young people who took part in the EUYD11 standardised survey totally or to a large extent agree that engagement in various mobility opportunities helps them to be more active in their communities, society, or Europe (Figure 6.2).

Figure 6.2

Multiple NWG and NYC reports highlighted that **young people in the consultation saw the connection between the EU youth programmes and active citizenship as strong, but not always explicit**. Young people said the programmes naturally support active citizenship by exposing participants to new perspectives, encouraging teamwork, and strengthening a sense of belonging to Europe, but that this could be made more intentional. Although the participants described the experience as transformative, particularly in terms of personal development, language learning, and gaining confidence, many did not initially connect these experiences with broader civic competencies. It was argued that whilst the personal dimension side of the programmes was well realised, the link to civic competences could still be more intentional as tools for nurturing democratic values, community involvement, and European solidarity.

‘Despite the positive experiences, young people point out that they often perceive Erasmus primarily as an academic or cultural experience, rather than as an EU project promoting active citizenship or political participation. For most, Erasmus remains a school project not directly linked to understanding the workings of the EU or encouraging their social engagement.’

Slovenian NWG Report

To link citizenship skills more explicitly to the programme, three general areas of improvement were highlighted across the reports.

- 1) Increasing the pedagogical support and training opportunities provided**, so that more projects contain strong formal and non-formal learning opportunities explicitly linked to citizenship. Specific suggestions for this included adding training components on civic education, democratic participation, youth rights, human rights, EU awareness, the EU values, and interculturality. Specific training modules could be added to learning mobilities, perhaps even on a mandatory basis.

‘Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps should integrate educational pathways on the EU, its values and democratic functioning and European citizenship rights: the inclusion of mandatory modules, even in non-formal form, on these topics would strengthen the awareness and civic engagement of participants.’

Italian NWG Report

- 2) Stronger follow-on activities after the end of each mobility** would give participants the opportunities to volunteer and apply their civic skills in some form of local solidarity or volunteering projects. It was said that many young people return from mobility experiences with essential skills, but without the tools to act in their community. There was a need to help transition short-term participation into long-term civic engagement and leadership (See topic: Volunteering and Solidarity).
- 3) Using the programmes to enhance intercultural dialogue and actively combat discrimination.** According to the Hungarian NWG, *‘Erasmus+ already builds friendships and reshapes views on Europe. To deepen this, programmes should further encourage dialogue around diversity, cultural exchange, and solidarity...to support the idea of an EU based on mutual understanding and cohesion.’*

Inclusion and Accessibility of the EU Youth Programmes

According to the results of the EUYD11 standardised survey, in general, young people with fewer opportunities see mobility opportunities as more beneficial than their counterparts from the majority group. In addition, young people from financially comfortable backgrounds, women, and young people who are in education, employment, or training are more likely to see the mobility opportunities as beneficial to their active citizenship development compared to their respective counterparts.

Inclusion and accessibility were widely discussed topics amongst the qualitative consultation respondents. It was clear that enhancing the accessibility of the programmes was a priority for

the large majority of NWGS and NYCs. There was concern that the current generation of youth programmes was not equally accessible and was perceived as intended for more privileged young people.

'Many [young people] expressed concern that access remains unequal, with urban youth, university students, or those in better-funded schools disproportionately benefiting. Meanwhile, young people in rural areas, vocational schools, or outside of formal education often remain unaware of these opportunities or perceive them as "not for people like me."

Polish NWG Report

'Several young people shared that they felt excluded due to ... the assumption that they lacked the "right profile" to apply. Some said they feared being the only person from their background in a group, or that they wouldn't feel safe or understood abroad.'

Dutch NWG Report

NWGs identified specific barriers to young people with fewer opportunities accessing the programmes, and these included:

- **Lack of information** about the programme and **lack of access to support** when applying (see topic: Awareness).
- **Complexity of language** within programme information materials and application forms (see topic: Administrative and Technical barriers).
- **Financial barriers associated with the programmes.** The Erasmus Student Network highlighted that, according to their research, over one-third of students experience significant difficulties securing affordable housing during Erasmus+ exchanges.

'Economically disadvantaged youth and those living outside major cities also voiced concerns about affordability - not necessarily of the programme itself, which is often funded, but of associated costs, such as preparation, travel, or missed income. A few young people said they work part-time or have family responsibilities that make participation in long-term mobility programmes difficult.'

Estonian NWG Report

Proposals to enhance accessibility and inclusion included:

- **Reducing the complexity** of application forms and **simplifying the language** used in programme information materials.
- **Increasing the levels of financial support** available through the programs to young people with fewer opportunities.
- **Creation of shorter-term or new formats** with emphasis on project formats which require less time commitment or travelling to enable young people with work or family commitments to participate, and to create a *'first step'* opportunity for those who were uncertain about participating.

- **Creation of accessibility standards** to take into account the specific needs of supporting different groups of young people with fewer opportunities.

Targeted and tailored outreach support for young people with fewer opportunities was also widely emphasised. It was said to be important to go beyond youth organisations and universities, and reach settings such as vocational schools, rural areas, and youth work settings. The role of **mentors or alumni** who could both provide support and act as inspiration was also highlighted.

'Mentors or alumni from similar backgrounds could visit schools, share their stories, and help others navigate the process. One young person suggested that "if someone from my town had done it and talked about it, I'd believe I could too".'

Estonian NWG Report

The EU Youth Programmes and Addressing New Challenges

Responses to the consultation question on the EU youth programmes did not generally address this topic. It was primarily discussed by the non-EU NYCs and by the INGYOs.

The World Organisation of the Scout Movement raised concerns over environmental sustainability, climate justice, and peace and security. They argued that for the EU to remain a robust humanitarian actor, it must ensure the stability of funding for youth organisations to address these topics through non-formal education.

Building on this, the Belarusian NYC and the Turkish NYC highlighted the critical role the programs played in **supporting youth NGOs and human rights activists in countries with a shrinking civic space**, or where fundamental rights were under threat. They highlighted the potential that the programmes could play in providing direct funding to these organisations from the EU. They stressed the need for this funding to be delivered with either no national government interference or robust and transparent allocation mechanisms. This was felt to be essential to avoid the risk of Governments that were not supportive of rights-based youth NGOs diverting funding away from these organisations. Finally, the Ukrainian NYC highlighted the critical role the programs could play in conflict-affected areas as part of peace-building processes.

To address some of these issues, it was argued that there was a need for non-EU organisations to have stronger access to the programmes (see topic: Geographic Scope).

Young People's Awareness of the EU Youth Programmes

Improving young people's awareness of the EU youth programmes was widely highlighted as an area for improvement within the consultation. There was a general view that the programmes are not well known enough amongst young people, and that many perceive them as specifically aimed at university students. There was also a concern that communication was unevenly distributed and did not effectively reach young people with fewer opportunities, and those outside of academic settings (see topic: Inclusion and Accessibility).

'Misconceptions remain, such as the belief that only university students can benefit from European mobility schemes, which leave out many groups, especially the younger ones or those who are not in higher education.'

French NWG Report

It was said that there is a need to **improve or reinvent the communication strategies** used for the EU youth programmes. Young people need to receive more accessible, transparent communication, in understandable language, with clear information about activities, costs and location, what to expect, how to prepare, and how participation can be of personal and professional benefit.

Suggestions from young people were highly consistent when it came to the types of communication methods that could be used:

- The creation of an **all-in-one platform** or app that gathers all EU youth programmes and opportunities in one place.
- Use of **social media** and communication channels that are already accessible, like Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube.
- Promoting the EU youth programmes more actively **in schools** (see topic: Formal Education).
- **Creative communications** such as photography or video contests, memes, and QR codes linking directly to applications.
- **Testimonials from past participants** to help make the programmes feel more accessible, especially to those with no prior experience.
- **Targeted outreach** to groups who are usually not reached or familiar with the EU youth programmes. This can be done through youth organisations and youth workers, as well as other methods.
- **Young ambassadors or alumni programmes** where young people share their personal experiences of mobility to help other young people understand the value and structure of these programs. Seeing peers successfully participate in Erasmus+ or ESC can help shift the perception that these are elite or inaccessible programmes and can inspire others to get involved.

Considering that **nearly all of the methods above are already in use** within the EU youth programmes, there is a need to improve, enhance or expand the existing approaches.

The Geographical Scope of the EU Youth Programmes

Within the consultation, National Youth Councils (NYC) from the EU Candidate countries and potential candidate countries were the only respondents to comment on the geographical scope of the EU youth programmes. However, the consultation question did not explicitly request exploring this sub-topic.

The NYCs from Albania, Belarus, Kosovo, Moldova, Montenegro and Ukraine, who are all currently third countries not associated with the Erasmus+ Programme³, called for full association of their countries to the EU youth programmes. There were several general arguments made for the inclusion of non-EU countries into the EU youth programmes:

- **To increase opportunities for young people in those countries.**
- **To support the EU accession processes in those countries.**
- **To enable organisations based in those countries to apply directly for Erasmus+ grants**, enhancing local ownership, strengthening organisational capacity, and increasing the number and relevance of projects led by and for young people from those countries.
- **To combat or counter restrictions on youth civil society** in some non-EU countries and counteract anti-EU propaganda.

On the final point, the Belarusian NYC highlighted the criminalisation of youth civil activism in Belarus and the need to consider how the EU youth programmes can support youth organisations and activists excluded from Belarus, for instance by recognising exiled democratic civil society organisations as eligible partners and allowing youth in exile to participate as Belarusian representatives, regardless of current residency.

‘For Moldovan youth, participation in Erasmus+ and ESC projects has a profound impact on how they perceive the EU, increases their confidence in cooperation, fosters mutual respect, and develops transversal skills. Therefore, we are convinced that expanding access to these programmes for candidate countries is a crucial element in achieving European Youth Goal #1.’

Moldovan NYC Report

The NYC of North Macedonia (a third country associated with the Erasmus+ programme) highlighted the need for the EU candidate countries to have access to financial and structural support for the establishment of an EUYD National Working Group. It was argued that it would enhance meaningful and structured youth participation, which was seen as crucial for the EU integration processes. The Belarusian NYC also called for permanent access to the EU Youth Dialogue.

In addition to full participation in the EU youth programmes, the need to establish ‘*national support centres*’ or ‘*coordinating structures*’ within non-EU countries that would fulfil the functions of the National Agencies for Erasmus+ was highlighted.

Speaking to concerns about government control of youth civil society, the Belarusian NYC underlined the need for the EU youth programmes to bypass the national government. The

³ <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/programme-guide/part-a/eligible-countries>

Turkish NYC also raised concerns about the need for stronger accountability measures and that Erasmus+ funding in Turkey was being diverted away from youth organisations towards government-backed organisations.

Administrative and Technical Barriers of the EU Youth Programmes

A strong message from the EUYD consultation was that application processes for grants were too complex, and young people needed both **simplification of application procedures** and a reduction in bureaucracy, along with an increase in support for young people to engage with applications:

'Application procedures must be simplified and designed to avoid excessive bureaucracy. Where complexity remains unavoidable, support structures and contact persons should be made available.'

Austrian NWG Report

Considering the types of support needed, having **local mentors, support staff, or youth workers who can guide young people** through the process was seen as crucial for addressing application complexity. Consultation respondents emphasised the importance of being able to get help with understanding the rules and filling out forms. This was said to be especially important for young people applying independently rather than through organisations or institutions. Some NWGs highlighted a need for an increase in National Agency staffing to provide this type of support.

'Participants propose the creation of "Youth Participation Hubs" at national or regional levels to offer personalised support, mentorship, and translation assistance. Enhanced digital platforms should also streamline the process.'

Greek NWG Report

Some consultation respondents proposed a need to **diversify project formats**, with a particular emphasis on supporting **low financial value, short-term project formats** that could use simplified application procedures.

'Not all young people can commit to long-term mobility or international volunteering. Therefore, more short-term, local and inclusive formats ... should be available and promoted equally. These can serve as first steps into civic engagement for young people with fewer opportunities.'

Polish NWG Report

Other NWGs noted the importance of **longer project durations** to enhance both the quality and sustainability through providing more consistent funding to youth organisations and youth projects.

The ESN raised the need to **increase funding within project grants**. They argued that implementing **real-cost calculations**, rather than flat-rate grants, would ensure funding reflects actual living expenses in host countries, noting that many Erasmus+ participants

struggled with affordable accommodation. They further stated that pre-departure grant payments would immediately alleviate the pre-mobility financial stress of individuals.

At the same time, some consultation respondents proposed changes that could increase the complexity of application processes. The German NWG were strongly critical of the '*lottery system*' used to allocate the Discover-EU places, arguing it was not inclusive and should be rethought. The Turkish NYC argued for the need for '*depoliticised, transparent and criteria-based allocation mechanisms, with independent oversight*' of grants and '*grievance redress and appeal processes for project applicants*' to ensure better accountability.

Chapter 7: The EU Youth Goals

The sixth part of the consultation was based around the following guiding question: *‘What updates might be needed to the European Youth Goals, as part of revising the EU Youth Strategy?’* This section explores the results linked to this question. The goal of this element of the consultation was to explore what aspects of the EU Youth Goals might need revising through of any future participatory process, and not to generate specific updates.

Importance of the Existing EU Youth Goals to Young People

Participants of the EUYD11 standardised survey were offered an opportunity to share to what extent the European Youth Goals priorities are still important to them (Figure 7.1). 73% of young people considered mental health and well-being to be totally or to a large extent important. Many other priorities are also rated high by over 70% of young people, such as sustainability, quality of learning and employment, or participation in policymaking. Nevertheless, many of the European Youth Goals priorities are no longer considered very important by 40% of young people, such as the connection between youth and the EU, conditions of youth organisations in the EU, or conditions in rural areas.

Young people from financially comfortable backgrounds, women, and young people in employment education or training were more likely to see the European Youth Goals as important than less financially comfortable young people, men, and NEETs. Young people with fewer opportunities, however, see the European Youth Goals as more important than their counterparts from the majority.

These results can be compared to results from the Eurobarometer 545 "Youth and democracy" (2024, see Figure 7.2), which show that, indeed, the European Youth Goals do not include some of the topics young people find important today, such as peace and security, economic and social well-being, or promoting human rights and democracy. On the other hand, some of the European Youth Goals seem to be very high on young people's agenda, and these topics were not included in the Eurobarometer survey, such as mental health and wellbeing, or increasing youth involvement in political decision-making in the EU.

All in all, while some European Youth Goals are supported by over 70% of the young people who took part in the EUYD11 standardised survey, some are only supported by slightly over half of them. This suggests that the European Youth Goals could be updated to align with the priorities of young people today.

Are the following topics important for you today?

Figure 7.1

What do you expect of the European Union for your generation?

multiple answers possible, EU-27, base n=26189, all respondents

Figure 7.2 Results from Q12 Eurobarometer 745

Potential New Themes for the EU Youth Goals

Within the qualitative consultation, a number of topics that were not strongly connected to the existing youth goals were proposed across the various reports. Mirroring the Eurobarometer results, two themes were prevalent.

- **Peacebuilding, security and protection from radicalisation** (or similar), where concerns were expressed about global threats relating to war and extremism, as well as strengthening democratic resilience in relation to this.
- **Economic security/cost of living and housing** (or similar).

There were also a number of calls to address concerns about **digitalisation**, incorporating topics such as media and information literacy, digital privacy, and the impact of AI. Concerns about disinformation and misinformation were raised as part of this, especially linked to the protection from radicalisation theme above. Arguably, this theme fits into the **European Youth Goal #4 Information and Constructive Dialogue**, though, as some reports highlighted, it could also be addressed through a standalone goal relating to digitalisation.

Some consultation reports also made proposals for specific new goals; however, these proposals were either partially aligned with other goals or were on topics not mentioned within other reports.

Updates to the Current European Youth Goals

Considering all of the comments received across the consultation reports, it was clear that some of the European Youth Goals themes were more widely commented upon than others.⁴ This did not necessarily indicate that these Goals are in greater need of revision; in many cases, comments emphasised the rising importance of some Goals or proposed ideas that were, to some extent, already addressed within the scope of the European Youth Goals as a whole.

Across the consultation reports, comments were more widely received in relation to topics linked to:

- **YG#1 Connecting the EU With Youth.** Although widely commented upon, most comments related to a general strengthening of this Goal, particularly to improve the effectiveness of youth participation mechanisms. In this sense, many of the proposals are already addressed by the Goal. However, the need for targeted information campaigns and innovative digital tools to engage young people in the EU decision-making was mentioned by multiple reports.
- **YG#4 Information and Constructive Societies.** Comments on this Goal were discussed above in relation to digitalisation.
- **YG#5 Mental Health and Wellbeing.** Although a number of comments were received on this, reflecting the results of the Eurobarometer 745 and EUYD11 standardised survey (above), the general trend was to stress the importance of this Goal, calling for it to be prioritised within the upcoming EU Youth Strategy. Some comments also emphasised the importance of recognising the structural causes of mental health issues of young people.
- **YG#8 Quality Learning.** Although a range of comments were received relevant to this Goal, they principally reflected topics and themes that were already addressed within the Goal. Emphasis was placed on the importance of civic education and life skills.
- **YG#9 Space and Participation for All.** A range of comments were received relating to this Goal. They typically emphasised the need to strengthen the elements relating to structured and permanent mechanisms for youth participation, enhancing the influence of young people through youth participation, and the provision of civic education.
- **YG#10 Sustainable Green Europe.** A range of comments suggested that this Goal should address climate justice and a just transition to green energy more effectively. There was a general sentiment that the Goal should be strengthened to reflect the increasing urgency of the climate crisis, focusing on structural causes of climate change and related inequality more than the current formations, which relate to

⁴ The consultation reporting did not require NWGs, INGYOS or non-EU NYCs to comment on specific goals, though many chose to do so. This section considered all the various proposals and comments whether explicitly linked to a youth goal or not.

environmental awareness. As the Dutch NWG reports stated, *'A revised goal could better address intergenerational equity, structural inequalities, and the need for youth to participate in shaping transition policies.'*

Across the consultation reports, comments were less widely received in relation to topics linked to:

- **YG#2 Equality of all Genders.** A very small number of comments were received relevant to this Goal, with no general trend or themes emerging.
- **YG#3 Inclusive Societies.** Several reports highlighted the need for explicit reference to combating discrimination within this Goal. There were also comments that inclusion should be addressed as a cross-cutting priority across all of the Goals.
- **YG#6 Moving Rural Youth Forward.** A minority of reports highlighted that this Goal could be better framed as *'equal access to opportunities in all regions of Europe'* or decentralisation of opportunities. The idea being that the Goal would focus more on improving structures and conditions rather than the youth themselves, as suggested by the title of the current European Youth Goal number 6. Moreover, some NWGs underlined that the topic of transportation in rural areas is not explicitly mentioned in the current Goal.
- **YG#7 Quality Employment for All.** A small number of comments were received relevant to this Goal, with no overall theme emerging and generally minor changes proposed.
- **YG#11 Youth organisations and European Programmes.** A very small number of comments were relevant to this Goal. The comments addressed ideas which are already prevalent in the other Goals, and there was no overall emerging theme.

Summary

Overall, the results suggest that the EU Youth Goals still have a high degree of relevance to young people today. However, it is clear that some goals, especially Mental Health and Sustainability, are of higher priority to young people than others.

Considering the need for revision to the current goals, the consultation suggests there may be a potential to develop goals relating to **peacebuilding, security, and protection from radicalisation** (or similar), and **economic security/cost of living and housing** (or similar). These are topics that have not been strongly addressed by the EUYD in the past and may require dedicated consultation with young people.

In addition, some of the existing goals might also be updated, namely

- **YG#4** to address more strongly the topic of digitalisation.
- **YG#9** to focus more strongly on youth participation (rather than youth spaces), reflecting this as an ongoing priority for young people frequently raised within EUYD consultations. This might draw on the results of EUYD8 and EUYD9.
- **YG#10** to address more strongly the topic of climate justice and incorporate newer thinking on sustainability. This might draw on the results of EUYD9.

As expected in a consultation the size of EUYD11, proposals for minor changes and additions to many other parts of the European Youth Goals were given across the various consultation reports. It is always the case that some actors and some young people will have preferences for particular formulations or priorities over others. However, there is a lack of strong consensus or trends within comments relating to the remaining Goals (1-3,5-8 & 11). As such, the consultation identified no overall strong call for a substantial revision of these Goals, acknowledging that some individual stakeholders may still wish for revisions. Some working group reports even commented that the current European Youth Goals were still generally suitable and relevant.

The various consultation reports also highlighted **the importance of developing any revision of the European Youth Goals in a participatory manner with young people**. In particular, it was stressed that any updating or revising of the European Youth Goals should be done via a similar participatory exercise, as their creation during the 7th Cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue: both in scope and in the palette of participatory mechanisms offered to young people.

As well as comments on the content of the goals, some reports also highlighted the need for **greater visibility** of the European Youth Goals, as well as the potential for them to become more specific, measurable and action-oriented, allowing progress towards them to be measured as a means of **accountability**.

Chapter 8: Consultation Methods and Participant Backgrounds in the EUYD11

Background and Overview of the EUYD11 Consultation

The EUYD11 consultation phase ran from January 2025 to July 2025. During this time, NWGs in the Member States of the European Union conducted consultation activities with young people on the themes of the cycle.

To inform the consultation activities, a thematic framework and methodological guidance were created by the researchers supporting the EUYD11, under the guidance of the EUYD11 European Steering Group. Guiding questions were developed to support this exercise (they are quoted at the beginning of each chapter of this report), and NWGs were asked to use a variety of consultation methods with young people, with an emphasis on qualitative, meaningful participation. Each NWG produced a report of its consultation findings.

INGYOs, as well as NYCs from the EU candidacy countries and potential candidacy countries, were asked to submit an expert statement report on the theme of the EUYD11. These INGYOS and NYCS are not expected to engage directly with young people to conduct EUYD consultation, but instead draw on their existing experience and past engagement activities.

NWG reports were received from all EU Member States, a total of 29 reports, since Belgium submits three reports, one for each community. Following a funding issue, the Croatian NWG report was received too late after the deadline to be included within the primary analysis; only data about the number of participants and methods were used from this report. Five INGYOS and eleven NYCs from EU candidacy countries or potential candidacy countries supplied expert statements.

The information from these reports were thematically analysed by the researchers supporting EUYD11 to produce this consultation report.

The remainder of this chapter outlines the backgrounds of participants who took part in EUYD11 consultations and the methods used by NWGs. Data in this section reflects only the work of the NWGs.

Number of Participants Engaged by NWGs in the EUYD11

All in all, NWGs engaged **38,042 young people**. This represents an average of 1442 per country or 1324 per working group. 8815 participants were engaged on a 'meaningful' basis - defined as any activity where the young person is participating in dialogue with others for a continued period (e.g., face-to-face or online events, but not surveys and social media polls). This represents 326 per country or 303 per working group.

This is a substantial increase in overall numbers compared to EUYD10 (28,723), but a lower number of participants were engaged on a meaningful basis compared to EUYD10 (9831 in EUYD10, compared to 8815 in EUYD11).

Inclusivity of the EUYD11 NWG Consultation

Data on the background of 70.6% of participants was provided by NWGs (see Appendix: EUYD11 Participant Data). Based on this sample, the backgrounds of participants are shown in the table below (Figure 8.1). This is compared to the previous two cycles and the EU-27 benchmark target, which illustrates the proportion of young people expected from that background, had they been randomly selected from European youth. All data should be treated as estimates due to the limitations of the monitoring system.

	EUYD9	EUYD10	EUYD11	Benchmark target*
Gender	F = 63.7% M= 34.3% Other gender = 1.9%	F = 56.0% M= 42.2% Other gender = 1.8%	F=54.1% M=45.1% Other gender = 0.8%	Equal Male:Female Ratio
% of participants identifying as having a disability	19.2%	6.6%	4.2%	1.95%
% of participants identifying as being part of a religious minority group	20.8%	23.1%	9.2%	4.58%
% of participants identifying as being part of an ethnic minority group	20.3%	14.5%	9.6%	4.21%
% of participants identifying as LGB or sexuality other than heterosexual	28.0%	14.7%	14.6%	3.15%
% of participants who are not in education, employment, or training (NEET)	9.6%	14.5%	27.2%	11.0*** (applies to EUYD11 only)
% of participants who are living in rural areas	26.3%	30.1%	24.0%	32.25%
% of participants with no parent holding a university degree	-	48.6%	56.6%	-
% of participants taking part in EUYD for the first time	-	84.2%	92.1%	-

* Based on Moxon, D. & Barta, O., 2023, [Evaluation of Participant Inclusion levels within EUYD](#), EU-CoE Youth Department, Strasbourg.

** Based on the EUROSTAT NEET rate for EU-27 2024.

Figure 8.1

The results indicate that:

- The gender bias towards young women is decreasing, but **young women are still slightly overrepresented** within the consultation sample.
- The proportion of first-time participants has increased, and in EUYD11, **92.1% of participants were taking part for the first time.**
- **The minority groups** of young people with disabilities, or from ethnic, religious or sexual minorities, **are over-represented** within the consultation sample.
- The proportion of young people who are NEET has substantially increased in EUYD11, and NEETs are over-represented in the EUYD11 consultation. However, the majority of these participants come from a survey conducted by the Italian NWG. If the Italian data is excluded, 5.9% of young people in the consultation are NEET, and NEETs are still underrepresented.
- **The proportion of young people from rural areas has fallen**, and in EUYD11, they are underrepresented.
- The proportion of young people with no parent holding a university degree has increased. This is used as a crude measure of socio-economic background. It can be concluded that **the number of young people from lower socio-economic backgrounds has increased.**

The age groups of participants of the EUYD11 consultations are shown in the graph below (Figure 8.2).

Age of participants

Figure 8.2

Methods Used by NWGs during the EUYD11 Consultation

During EUYD11, NWGs used a wide range of methods to engage with young people, with nearly all using a mixture of methods. The most popular being face-to-face events, followed by a survey based on the standard survey questions.

Method	Proportion of NWGS using this method
Participatory video / Participatory photo competitions	7%
Other methods	17%
Simple social media polls (not including surveys)	28%
Online EUYD events	28%
A survey which was not based on the standard survey questions	35%
A survey based on the standard survey questions	69%
Face-to-face EUYD events	97%

Figure 8.3

Use of the EUYD11 standardised survey

The NWGs were supplied with a set of standard survey questions to translate and use in their own online surveys if they wished. 12 NWGs supplied data from their surveys, which were aggregated into a common European data set. This chapter summarises characteristics of the EUYD11 standardised survey sample. All shares are rounded to the nearest whole number.

After cleaning, there were responses from 8379 young people, aged 13 to 34, within this data set. As was the case in the past, even in EUYD11, the sample of the standardised survey was weighted to avoid over- or under-representing young people from different countries. The Eurostat data 2024 on the youth population per country were used to calculate weights, and the weighted EUYD11 standardised survey sample well reflected the reality of youth populations in the given countries, as can be seen in Figure 8.4. The weighted sample was therefore used for all analyses of the EUYD11 standardised survey.

NWG Country: Unweighted Sample		Eurostat: Youth Population per Country	NWG Country: Weighted Sample		
1 Austria	7.6%	1 Austria	4.8%	1 Austria	4.8%
2 France	11.8%	2 France	37.7%	2 France	37.7%
3 Malta	5.7%	3 Malta	0.3%	3 Malta	0.3%
4 Netherlands	1.2%	4 Netherlands	10.2%	4 Netherlands	10.4%
5 Portugal	3.6%	5 Portugal	5.1%	5 Portugal	5.0%
6 Romania	13.7%	6 Romania	9.7%	6 Romania	9.7%
7 Sweden	6.5%	7 Sweden	6.0%	7 Sweden	6.0%
8 Poland	16.6%	8 Poland	18.6%	8 Poland	18.5%
9 Finland	12.3%	9 Finland	3.1%	9 Finland	3.1%
10 Slovenia	1.2%	10 Slovenia	1.0%	10 Slovenia	1.0%
11 Cyprus	17.4%	11 Cyprus	0.5%	11 Cyprus	0.5%
12 Bulgaria	2.4%	12 Bulgaria	2.9%	12 Bulgaria	2.8%
Total	100.0%	Total	100.0%	Total	100.0%

Figure 8.4

The EUYD11 standardised survey sample (see Figure 8.5) contained answers from 59% of women, 39% men, and 2% identifying as other gender. Across the entire sample, 19% of young people said they were working full-time, and 18% were working part-time. 63% said they were in full-time education or training, and 11% were in part-time education or training.

Gender		Are you...		Are you...	
1 Male	39%	1 Working full time	19%	1 In full time education or training	63%
2 Female	59%	2 Working part time	18%	2 In part time education or training	11%
3 Other gender	2%	3 Not working	63%	3 Not in education or training	27%
Total	100%	Total	100%	Total	100%

Figure 8.5

About 9% of the EUYD11 standardised survey sample were not in education, employment, or training (NEET), and 91% were in some form of education, employment or training (see Figure 8.6). Young people of majority origin constituted slightly less than half of the sample, and about half were young people with fewer opportunities, i.e., those young people belonged to at least one minority group (ethnic or religious minority, sexual minority, young people with disabilities or rural youth).

Are you...		Are you...	
1 Young people in employment, education or training	91%	1 Majority youth	46%
2 Young NEETs	9%	2 Young people with fewer opportunities	54%
Total	100%	Total	100%

Figure 8.6

In more detail, the minority groups were represented as follows (see Figure 8.7): There were between 8% and 28% of young people from various minority backgrounds, with the most

represented group being young people from rural areas, and the least represented being young people with disabilities.

Do you consider yourself to be part of an ethnic minority?		Do you consider yourself to be part of a religious minority?		Do you consider yourself to be lesbian, gay, bisexual or any sexuality other than heterosexual?		Do you consider yourself to be disabled?		Do you consider yourself to be living in a rural or remote area?	
1 Yes	14%	1 Yes	17%	1 Yes	23%	1 Yes	8%	1 Yes	28%
2 No	86%	2 No	83%	2 No	77%	2 No	92%	2 No	72%
Total	100%	Total	100%	Total	100%	Total	100%	Total	100%

Figure 8.7

About 12% of the sample were young people who felt very comfortable financially, and about 8% were worrying about their finances all the time (Figure 8.8). Generally, however, the most populated groups were those in the middle of the scale (rank 3 or 4), who felt neither very rich nor very poor, and these were about 50% of the sample. Comparison in the results of this report between young people in financially comfortable situations and less financially comfortable situations is a comparison between groups 1 and 6.

How comfortable are you in your life when it comes to money?	
1 I am very comfortable, I never worry about finances	12%
2	15%
3	28%
4	25%
5	12%
6 I am not comfortable at all, I worry about finances all the time	8%
Total	100%

Figure 8.8

Lastly, 86% of the young respondents never took part in any EUYD activity, and 60% of the sample came from families with a university degree (see Figure 8.9).

Have you taken part in an EU youth dialogue activity before?		Do either of your parents have a university degree?	
1 Yes	14%	1 Yes	60%
2 No	86%	2 No	40%
Total	100%	Total	100%

Figure 8.9

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